

The Effects of Employee Management Information System (SIMPEG), Workplace Environment and Human Resources Quality on Performance through Employee Motivation to Digital System

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ABSTRACT

Human resources with quality and high standard are highly needed in the execution of good government. The working unit of SDA (Water Resources) at Wampu Besitang, Water Resources Agency, and the Public Works and Spatial Planning of North Sumatera Province are expected to be able to carry out various duties in order to realize their plans in development planning programs which are basically conducted participatively, transparently and accountably. The performance that is below expectation is resulted from the duties that are not well accomplished. The objective of this research was to examine and analyze the effects of Employee Management Information System, workplace environment and human resources quality on performance through employee motivation to digital system. The research problems were whether employee management information system workplace environment and human resources quality had some effects on performance through employee motivation to Digital System. The population was all employees from either structural or functional levels i.e. 108 employees. The samples consisted of 108 people, selected by saturated sampling technique. This research employed descriptive analytical method. The data were assisted with Smart PLS software. The results demonstrated that employee management information system had positive and significant effects on employee motivation, employee management information system had

positive and significant effects on performance, workplace environment did not have any positive and significant effect on employee motivation, workplace environment did not have any positive and significant effect on employee performance, indicating that workplace environment did not have any significant impacts on improvement of employee motivation, human resources quality had positive and significant effects on employee motivation, human resources quality had positive and significant effects on employee performance, employee motivation had positive and significant effects on employee performance, employee motivation as the intervening variable did not have any positive and significant impacts on the effects of employee management information system on employee performance, employee motivation as the intervening variable did not have any positive and significant impacts on the effects of workplace environment on employee performance, employee motivation as the intervening variable had positive and significant impacts on the effects of human resources quality on employee performance. The research results demonstrated that Q-square was 0.937. It indicated that the variants of the research data that could be explained by the research model was 93,7%, while the rest 6,3% was explained by the other factors that were not included in this research.

Keywords: Employee Management Information System, Workplace Environment, Human Resources Quality, Performance and Motivation

INTRODUCTION

Every organization or company will always try to improve performance in the hope that what the company's goals will be achieved. According to Mangkunegara (2013: 67) performance is the result of quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Human resources are a very dominant factor in influencing employee performance.

In addition, good performance professionalism is how an employee is able to show work behavior that leads to the achievement of company goals and objectives, for example by managing human resources to lead to good work results. Work results are influenced by many factors including work motivation. Motivation is divided into two theories namely, satisfaction theory and process theory. Satisfaction theory focuses on the factors within individuals that encourage, direct, maintain and stop behavior. Satisfaction can occur if the service is carried out to the maximum so there will be an interest again to do it again (Indah Lestari; Endang Sulistya Rini 2020). Process theory explains and analyzes how behavior is driven, directed and processed.

George and Jones (2012: 12) argue that motivation is central in management, which governs how people behave and how they complete work within the organization. With the motivation that has been formed it will lead to loyalty in the organization, so that the organization formed becomes increasingly systemized. Loyalty created will form a strong organizational system and can lead to organizational growth and development (Indah Lestari et.al 2018). In facing the growth and development of an organization that is already so complex, it requires the availability of a management information system that is able to help provide data and information as material for determining development policies and strategies as well as for the availability of operational data and information.

Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 17 of 2000 stated that: "The Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) is an integrated totality consisting of processing equipment including procedure collectors, processing staff and software, storage devices including data centers and data banks and communication devices which are interrelated, interdependent and mutually determine in the context of providing information in the field of employment".

Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) is very important in providing services for all existing personnel, because employees are an important asset in the organization of an organization that must be managed properly. An integrated system in an Personnel Management System has a great influence on the performance of employees. The most dominant influence arises with the existence of information support tools in the form of technology in this case computers. The existence of technology in an organization becomes a very important stimulant given that with this technological tool systematic work can be carried out well and quickly. This is related to management principles, which are efficient and effective. Employees are required to be able to implement the existing staffing information system in an organization so that all activities can run more effectively and efficiently.

Information and communication technology currently has a very important role in various aspects, and affects the ease of communication and interaction that is more effective and efficient through E-Government. One model for the development of E-Government is Government to Government which aims to improve relations and cooperation between different levels of government with different locations as well as relationships between the central government and local governments such as sharing databases between local governments to the central government and Government to employees aimed at to improve the efficiency and

effectiveness of government administration such as the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG). This development is carried out to arrange human resource management through an up to date Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) in order to make decisions related to human resources such as enforcement of discipline, disciplinary violations, and appointment of employees in structural positions. In addition, the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) functions as a recording of employee data so that if necessary, documents can be downloaded directly without needing to ask the regional civil service agency except to be legalized.

Problems that occur in the input have not been able to manage the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) properly, in the operation of incomplete data will be processed, and in the output of employee data incompatibility with facts. These assumptions are caused by ineffective management of inputs, operations and expenditures so that the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) has not been running effectively by looking at input, operation and output indicators. The inhibiting factors include operational technical problems, for example, employees are still confused in operating this program, causing employees to not understand the procedures, limited human resources, not all employees can operate technology, technological means to apply the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG), and delays data update. The superior Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) is that which provides valid, transparent, integrated staffing information and the user is able to apply the system well so that the updating of information and data runs optimally.

Although technology provides benefits to the organization, sometimes implementation failures occur not because of the quality and capacity of the system, but due to the low level of user acceptance. Technology acceptance is a user's

willingness to use technology to support their work. When users are willing to accept technology, users will often use it (Teo, 2011). The Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) is also a program created to answer some of the challenges that will occur in the administration of personnel in the future, which is intended to assist in the management of staffing information and data that can produce valid, integrated and up-to-date power. This program is a place for employees who want to know information and staffing data in one system. When the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) program has not been implemented it has a disruptive impact on information and data stability because it uses high-risk manual methods such as lost, damaged documents, so that records in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Provincial Spatial Planning North Sumatra is not good.

In addition, the work environment is also a factor that needs to be considered because the work environment in the workplace is very important for an employee that will affect the resulting performance. A conducive work environment has a positive impact in the form of employee morale in relation to achieving company goals. Rahmawanti et al (2014) states that the work environment is all around the employee both physically and non-physically that can influence him in carrying out all the work delegated to him.

Organizations in achieving a goal must pay attention whether or not an employee is eligible to enter the organization. This can be reviewed with the quality of human resources in completing their tasks and responsibilities. The understanding of the quality of human resources according to According to Ndraha (2012: 12) says that the understanding of the quality of human resources, namely: Human resources are able to create not only comparative value, but also competitive-generative-innovative value by using the

highest energy such as intelligence, creativity, and imagination, no longer solely uses crude energy such as raw materials, land, water, muscle energy, and so on.

Quality human resources that meet the standards are needed in the implementation of good government. UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Provincial Spatial Planning North Sumatra is expected to be able to carry out various tasks in achieving plans in the development plan program which are basically implemented in a participatory, transparent and accountable manner. Organizational performance is reflected through employee performance. In the end, the assessment of employee performance plays an important role for organizations to create optimum human resource development programs.

UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province Is a Technical Implementation Unit that has the task of assisting the Head of Service in carrying out government affairs in the field of water resources management in irrigation areas, swamps, beaches, rivers, lakes and reservoirs. UPT SDA Wampu Besitang The Water Resources, Human Settlements and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province has carried out its main tasks and functions despite the limited personnel, equipment, documentation and financing that have sought to prepare and carry out in order to implement good government, in accordance with Regional Regulation No. 53 In 2018, that the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province has the task of carrying out the affairs of the Government / Provincial Authority in the field of Water Resources, Workshops and Spatial Planning and co-administration tasks.

Based on preliminary observations of research at the Center for Research and Development of Water Resources, it indicates that there are problems with employee performance at the agency. The

employee performance results were not as expected by the WT Besitang SDA office. From observations made the main tasks can not be completed properly.

One of them is a decrease in the number of employees who are still considered less to support the completion of work assignments in accordance with the stipulated time, the low quality of work produced by employees is that there are a number of jobs produced that are still less than optimal so that it inhibits other jobs because every task is done always procrastinating, the low initiative of employees, where employees do not use all of their work time with other things outside of work. Other phenomena that occur at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province can be seen from employees who work over time, are unable to handle conflicts, employees are also unable to accept changes in their work, and changes that occur usually in the case of the latest version of the application and the policies of the Agency and the lack of discipline applied can be seen from the number of jobs that cannot be completed on time for various reasons given.

Based on the results of an initial survey regarding employee motivation, it can be concluded that employee motivation is still low so that morale decreases .. Employees are still not motivated to do the work optimally and have not given the best results. Lack of employee motivation affects many things which certainly makes the work of employees become out of control, this is also caused by a system that is all based on digitalization while not all employees are able to adapt to the latest innovations. The technology used in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources Office, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province includes two ways namely manual and computerized. Both systems run together to complement each other's strengths and weaknesses in each system.

However, the lack of socialization and the unequal level of education of employees automatically impact the performance of the employees themselves due to their ability and expertise in processing computerized systems owned by these employees with little or no ability. Problems that occur in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Human Settlements and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province regarding information systems are quite diverse starting from attendance systems that have not been maximally used where there are still frequent absences on manual systems and E-attendance systems so in this case the impact on employee performance.

The information system presented by the Government of North Sumatra Province through the Regional Personnel Agency to the Regional Apparatus Organization called SIMPEG only contains employee data and is not equipped with regulatory or useful information for each section in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province which will certainly make it easier for employees to carry out their duties, the delivery of information is still oral. The employees who lack mastery of the application of SIMPEG such as inputting and editing data so that the effectiveness of employee work is reduced.

In addition, the working environment in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province also still needs attention. The work environment can be interpreted as a place in which there are several supporting facilities to achieve company goals in accordance with the vision and mission of the organization. But in this case there is a phenomenon of lack of employee comfort in the existing work environment.

Hypothesis

Based on the concept presented by the author, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

1. The staffing information system (SIMPEG) has a positive and significant effect on the motivation of staff at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the motivation of employees at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
3. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on the motivation of employees at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.
4. Personnel information system (SIMPEG) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
5. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
6. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
7. Motivation of employees has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.
8. Personnel information system (SIMPEG) has a positive and significant effect on performance through employee motivation at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.

9. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance through employee motivation in UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.
10. The quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on performance through employee motivation at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study uses quantitative methods that are associative, namely research that aims to determine the relationship of two or more variables. In this research, a theory can be developed that can function to explain, predict and control a symptom to produce an assessment (Sugiyono, 2016).

The population in this study were all employees of UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Department of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province. The intended employee includes all employees from both structural and general functional levels totaling 108 employees. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2012). The sampling technique in this study is the saturated sample technique that is all populations are sampled. So that the number of samples in this study amounted to 108 respondents.

Data collection techniques in research carried out by making a list of questions / questionnaire. The reason for using the questionnaire as a research instrument is that the questionnaire has a high position and has the ability to reveal the potential of the respondents. This technique gives the respondent the responsibility to read and answer questions and the researcher can provide an explanation of the purpose of the survey and questions that are less understood by the respondent and responses to the

questionnaire can be directly collected by the researcher after being filled in by the respondent and interview. Interview is the process of obtaining information for research purposes by means of question and answer. This interview was addressed directly to staff of UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Department of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.

The type of data collected is the type of qualitative and quantitative data sourced from primary and secondary data. Primary Data, namely research data obtained directly from the original source (not through an intermediary source) and data collected specifically to answer research questions in accordance with the wishes of researchers (Indriatoro and Supomo (2012: 129). Secondary data is data that is a source of data research obtained by researchers indirectly through intermediaries (obtained and recorded by other parties) Secondary data are generally in the form of evidence, notes, or historical reports that have been compiled in archives (documentary data) which are published and not published.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Influence of Staffing Information Systems (SIMPEG) Against Employee Motivation

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for the staffing information system (2.183) is greater than the value of the table (1.66), or the sig t value for the staffing information system (0.029) is smaller than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H_0 and accept H_1 , for the staffing information system (Simpeg). Thus, partially the staffing information system (Simpeg) has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation, that is. The direction of positive influence, meaning the better the staffing information system (Simpeg), the employee motivation will increase.

Another opinion was also conveyed by Rivai that the Civil Service information system is a systematic procedure for

collecting, storing, maintaining, attracting, validating the data needed by a company to improve decisions. This means that the staffing information system has the ability to obtain the information needed or the choice of many people who are more related to new planning activities.

In general the staffing information system can increase motivation because by providing accurate and efficient information, so that decision making can be done objectively. Strategically the application of the staffing information system is one of the systems engaged in staffing and is able to grow knowledge, maintain, enrich and provide knowledge in the field of staffing to parties who need it as a basis for making accurate decisions at the right time. The staffing management information system that is held quickly, accurately and accurately is intended to support the management policies of Civil Servants, especially in supporting the policy of fostering Civil Servants .

The condition of the Personnel Management Information System (SIMPEG) currently has an information system that is integrative, systematic, up-to-date, and easy and fast in obtaining employee data that is needed at any time in coaching related to efforts to improve employee quality. SIMPEG (Employee Management Information System) is defined as an integrated Information System, which includes employee data collection, data processing, procedures, work procedures, human resources and information technology to produce fast, complete and accurate information in order to support staffing administration.

SIMPEG as an employee information provider application handles staffing data management which has many advantages, namely fast processing of employee information data with computerized data processing can be done quickly, information that is processed accurately because of various validations and controls, the information conveyed is more concise and can be searched quickly

because it is stored in a storage media that can be accessed at any time, information is more secure, with user validation and user level, so that only authorized users can use staffing information, maintaining staffing information is relatively easy and simple and can be used to measure performance employees in processing and carrying out employee processes

The existence of simpeg is able to make employees more motivated to provide high work results. Because in this case simpeg makes employee work more effective and the data provided more accurate. This is in line with research conducted by the results of Lasmaya's research, (2016) and Saputra (2017) states that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on performance.

The results of the answers of the majority of respondents answered well and very well namely the ability to apply SIMPEG, able to enter personal data into SIMPEG, have the ability to add data to SIMPEG, able to edit SIMPEG data, able to provide personal data information into SIMPEG and able to provide personal information that is worth on SIMPEG.

In the characteristics of respondents who were the most male sex compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make a picture in clarifying the influence of the Personnel Information System (Simpeg) Against Employee Motivation.

Effect of Work Environment on Employee Motivation

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for the work environment (0.396) is smaller than the value of t table (1.66), or the sig t value for the work environment

(0.692) is greater than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, accepting H₀ and rejecting H₁. Thus partially the work environment does not have a positive and significant effect on employee motivation, meaning that the work environment does not have a real impact in increasing employee motivation.

The work environment is everything that is around the workers and which can affect themselves in carrying out the tasks that are carried out or that are their responsibilities. To increase employee motivation in carrying out tasks, an adequate work environment is needed. An employee will be able to work optimally if supported by a good working environment. A working environment is said to be good or appropriate if employees can carry out their activities optimally, healthy, safe, and comfortable.

The results of this study are not in line with previous studies by Nitisemito (2010: 183) suggesting that the work environment is all around workers who can influence themselves in carrying out the tasks assigned. Employees are able to optimize their abilities with a supportive work environment. This is in line with Heni Ingsiyah, (2017) that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on motivation.

The results of the answers of the majority of respondents answered well and very well ie the majority of respondents answered well from the statement of the respondent that had adequate lighting in the room, in the workroom had good air circulation, felt no noise at the office, got complete facilities at work, air temperature at the room is good so stay focused, have good communication with colleagues, have the opportunity to move forward, feel safe at work, have the opportunity to use your abilities and have a good relationship with your boss.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the

majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. However, this shows that the characteristics of the respondents did not show any influence between the work environment on employee motivation.

Effect of Quality of Human Resources on Work Motivation

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for HR Quality (7.674) is greater than the value of t table (1.66), or the value of sig t for the work environment (0,000) is smaller than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H₀ and accept H₁. Thus partially the quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation, meaning that the quality of human resources owned by employees will have a real impact in increasing employee motivation.

The quality of human resources is an important factor in carrying out work. Employees who have good quality will be better able to complete a task quickly. As according to Pasolong (2013) stated that the quality of human resources is a workforce that has a high competency of knowledge, skills and morale.

This is very necessary so that government management in regional autonomy can take place effectively and efficiently. What is needed is not only a sufficient amount, but also the quality of employees that must be measured by looking at their educational background, skills, work experience, rank levels and employment status. Ability is increasingly important because the leader gives work to his subordinates to do well and integrated to the desired goals.

This is in line with research conducted by Arini, (2015) that the company not only expects capable, capable, and skilled employees, but most importantly the company has employees who have quality so that they can improve their

existing abilities regarding the field of work carried out so far. In addition Munirat (2014), Martini, et al (2014) and tumbuan (2016) provide the same argument that in running an organization an understanding is needed to increase employee workforce through skilled workforce.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make clear the influence of the Quality of Human Resources on Employee Motivation.

The Effect of SIMPEG on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for the personnel information system (2.183) is greater than the value of t_{table} (1.66), or the sig t value for the personnel information system (0.029) is smaller than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H_0 and accept H_1 , for the staffing information system (Simpeg). Thus, partially the staffing information system (Simpeg) has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation, that is. The direction of positive influence, meaning the better the staffing information system (Simpeg), the employee motivation will increase.

Furthermore Simamora (2011: 90) argues that: "Personnel management information system is a systematic procedure for collecting, storing, maintaining, attracting, and validating data needed by an organization about human resources, personnel activities, characteristics of unit- organizational unit ". A good information system must be able to produce quality information that is useful in decision making because the information

must be able to reach the interests of management at various management levels.

The staffing management information system is a determining factor in achieving the expected performance; this is due to the fact that it helps the management process in an organization. Management covers the entire management hierarchy in an organization, starting from the top management hierarchy that is responsible for the success or failure of the organization as a whole to the lower management hierarchy which is only responsible for the daily operations of certain departments. This is in line with research conducted by Saputra, (2017) and Lasmaya (2016) which states that the employment information system has a positive and significant effect on performance. Then Abugabah, et al (2107) Munirat (2014) Khashman (2016) states that a company / organization is a process of activities within the company that takes place in it that must follow technological developments, in order to carry out the tasks given effectively and efficiently so that Management information systems greatly affect performance.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make clear the influence of SIMPEG on Employee Performance.

Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for the work environment (0.115) is smaller than the value of t_{table} (1.66), or the value of sig t for the work environment (0.909) is greater than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained then accept H_0 and reject H_1 . Thus partially the work

environment does not have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, meaning that the work environment does not have a real impact in improving employee performance.

For companies the effectiveness of employee performance is very important because it relates to the survival of the company. To achieve company goals, the effectiveness of employee performance is one of the factors that need to be considered. Another factor that also influences employee performance is work environment. The work environment includes everything that exists around the workers who can influence themselves in carrying out their duties. The work environment in a company is very important to be considered by management even though the work environment does not carry out the production process in a company, but the work environment has a direct influence on the employees who carry out the production process.

The influence of a comfortable work environment will improve employee performance. Conversely, an inadequate work environment will cause a decrease in employee performance and affect the level of decline in employee motivation. Therefore the role of the work environment is very dominant on the level of work motivation and employee performance in a company. Conversely an inadequate work environment will cause a decrease in employee performance and affect the level of decline in employee motivation. Therefore the role of the work environment is very dominant on the level of work motivation and employee performance in a company.

The work environment is an organizational element that has a strong influence on the formation of individual behavior in the organization and influences organizational performance. The work environment encompasses the socio-cultural environment and the physical environment. be a motivating and supporting factor for employees in carrying out their work,

because the work environment is a place for employees to do their work.

A good work environment is needed by employees because it can increase productivity due to decreased number of lost work days, increased efficiency and quality of workers who are more committed and greater flexibility and adaptability as a result of increased participation and a sense of ownership. This research is in line with the results of the study from Faiqoh et al. (2014) and Ningrum et al (2014) stated that the work environment has a positive effect on performance. The work environment will be able to influence employee performance, this is supported by the motivation of employees in completing existing tasks.

The results of the answers of the majority of respondents answered well and very well ie the majority of respondents answered well from the statement of the respondent that had adequate lighting in the room, in the workroom had good air circulation, felt no noise at the office, got complete facilities at work, air temperature at the room is good so stay focused, have good communication with colleagues, have the opportunity to move forward, feel safe at work, have the opportunity to use your abilities and have a good relationship with your boss.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. However, this shows that the characteristics of the respondents did not clarify the influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance.

Influence of SDM Quality on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing results show the tcount for HR Quality (1.994) is greater than the ttable value (1.66), or the sig t value for

the work environment (0.047) is smaller than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H0 and accept H1. Thus partially the quality of HR has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, meaning that the quality of HR owned by employees will have a real impact in improving employee performance.

Human resources are said to be of high quality when they have the ability to carry out the authority and responsibilities given to them. This capability can only be achieved if they have sufficient education, training and experience to carry out the tasks and responsibilities given. If employees do not have good quality, it will affect the resulting performance and will have an impact on the company.

Every employee is recommended to be able to have an attitude of professionalism at work in order to be able to optimize the skills, time, energy, knowledge and resources they have in accordance with the field they are undergoing, so that it will affect the performance carried out by employees. Qualified employees also have the reliability and expertise in carrying out tasks so that they are carried out with high quality, right time, meticulous, and with procedures that are easily understood. Qualified and professional employees must have a commitment to the company. Employees promise themselves to be able to advance the company in order to achieve a common goal with the best performance possible in the current conditions of global competition, because commitment is also an individual attachment to a company.

The ability of employees as human resources in an organization is very important meaning and existence to increase work productivity in an organizational environment. Humans are one of the most important elements that determine the success or failure of an organization to achieve its goals and develop its mission. Education and training produce a better workforce quality and increase work productivity. As well as environmental and

socio-cultural conditions. Low quality living conditions with a variety of pollution and low morale and people who feel they do not enjoy the work equitably will reduce the quality of work

The quality of human resources is a serious problem if it is associated with government performance which is considered still low. Human resources are very important for every organization, so they need to be managed, regulated and utilized so that they can function productively to achieve organizational goals, likewise the human resources owned by an organization need to be managed professionally in order to create a balance between employee needs and demands and abilities organization.

The quality of HR is very much needed because of the quality of HR will increase employee motivation in providing better performance. This is in line with research from Lasmaya, (2016) and Marini et al (2014) states that competence has a positive and significant effect on performance.

The results of the answers of the majority of respondents answered well and very well that had good health at work, had a strong physical condition, were able to reduce hazardous work, were able to protect themselves from work hazards, had supportive intellectual intelligence, education in the field of work was very supportive, had strength mentally in dealing with problems that occur in the office and competence supports increasing work effectiveness.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make clear the influence of the

Quality of Human Resources on Employee Performance.

Effect of Employee Motivation on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing results show the value of t for employee motivation (2.407) is greater than the value of t_{table} (1.66), or the value of $sig\ t$ for the work environment (0.016) is smaller than α (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus partially employee motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, meaning that the presence of employee motivation that comes from within and from outside quite well will have a real impact in improving employee performance.

The results of the answers of the majority of respondents answered well and very well namely the salary provided made motivated to work, additional income allowances provided in accordance with work results, health insurance provided according to needs, felt safe working at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang and career opportunities to be promoted according to the assessment.

Motivation greatly influences the success of an organization, especially in efforts to improve employee performance. Performance can be demonstrated by an increase in work results and increased employee work behavior including: self-development, integrity, building trust, professionalism, teamwork and attendance. By providing proper work motivation to employees to work better, employees will have enthusiasm in work so that work that is charged to employees can be completed more efficiently.

The results of this study are in line with previous studies by Siagian, T (2017) and Yatipai, (2015) who stated that motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. In addition Prakoso, (2014) Ingsiyah, (2017) Arini, (2015) and Muchtar, (2016) concluded that motivation has a significant influence on performance

and becomes an important point that must be considered.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make clear the influence of Employee Motivation on Employee Performance.

Indirect Effects of Employee Information Systems on Employee Performance Through Employee Motivation as Intervening Variables

Hypothesis testing results show the value of calculation for the influence of staffing information systems on employee performance through employee motivation as an intervening variable (1,399) smaller than the value of t_{table} (1.66), or the $sig\ t$ value for the effect of staffing information systems on employee performance through employee motivation as employees intervening variable (0.163) is greater than α (0.05). Based on the results obtained, accept H_0 and reject H_1 . Thus, partially employee motivation as an intervening variable does not have a positive and significant impact in showing the effect of the staffing information system (Simpeg) on employee performance, that is. The direction of the negative influence, meaning indirectly the motivation of employees does not have a real impact in increasing the influence of the staffing information system (Simpeg) on employee performance.

Information systems are data and procedures that work together in a coordinated manner. The emphasis lies on the concept of a system that shows that the various components involved in it functionally and cooperatively achieve the same goal. Functional activities and healthy HR decisions, one of which is based on the

availability of good and quality HR information. Acquisition and information retrieval is very necessary to achieve company goals because the information as a source of evaluation of the development of organizations, institutions, companies and departments.

The results of this study are not in line with previous studies by Iasmaya, (2016) and Saputra (2017) state that management information systems have a positive and significant effect on performance. Simpeg is able to handle management in an organization, starting from the top management hierarchy that is responsible for the success or failure of the organization as a whole to the lower management hierarchy which is only responsible for the daily operations of certain departments. Abugabah, et al (2017) Nurhayati, (2016) Munirat (2014), Khashman (2016) concluded that the employee's ability to use and study management information systems and utilize information generated in helping work completion and improving employee performance.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. However, this shows that the characteristics of the respondents did not clarify the influence of the employment information system on Employee Performance through SIMPEG Employee Motivation on Employee Performance.

The majority of respondents answered very well and well to the statement for employee performance that is having good health at work, having a strong physical condition, being able to reduce hazardous work, being able to protect themselves from work hazards, having supporting intellectual intelligence,

education in the field of work is very support, have mental strength in dealing with problems that occur in the office and competence supports improving work effectiveness

The Indirect Effect Of The Work Environment On Employee Performance Through Employee Motivation As An Intervening Variable

Hypothesis testing results show the value of the Calculation for the Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance through Employee Motivation as an intervening variable (0.373) smaller than the value of table (1.66), or the sig t value for the Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance through Employee Motivation as an Intervening variable (0.709) is greater than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, then accepting H0 and rejecting H1. Thus, partially employee motivation as an intervening variable does not have a positive and significant impact in showing the influence of the work environment on employee performance, meaning. which is evident in increasing the influence of the work environment on employee performance.

Work environment is a relationship that occurs with employees in the workplace. Everything that is in the workplace is a work environment. Employees are in a work environment when the employee performs work activities, and all forms of relationships that involve the employee, including from the work environment. Work environment measurement indicators are based on sub-components of the work environment, and can be explained as follows measurement of the work environment of the technological environment, human environment, and organizational environment which exists.

The results of this study are not in line with previous studies by Faiqoh et al, (2014) and Ningrum et al (2014) states that the work environment has a positive effect on performance. The performance in

question is completing tasks quickly because of the comfort in working due to an adequate work environment both physical and non-physical which is directly related to the work of the employee. The same that the work environment is able to improve performance through motivation. To achieve company goals, work motivation is very important for employees because motivation can provide encouragement and enthusiasm so that employee work is more optimal.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. However, this shows that the characteristics of the respondents did not clarify the influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance through SIMPEG Employee Motivation on Employee Performance.

The majority of respondents answered very well and well to the statement for employee performance that is having good health at work, having a strong physical condition, being able to reduce hazardous work, being able to protect themselves from work hazards, having supporting intellectual intelligence, education in the field of work is very support, have mental strength in dealing with problems that occur in the office and competence supports improving work effectiveness.

The Indirect Effect Of Human Resources Quality On Employee Performance Through Employee Motivation As An Intervening Variable

Hypothesis testing results indicate the value of the Influence of HR Quality on Employee Performance through Employee Motivation as an intervening variable (2.262) greater than the ttable value (1.66),

or the sig t value for the Effect of HR Quality on Employee Performance through Employee Motivation as an Intervening variable (0.024) is smaller than alpha (0.05). Based on the results obtained, reject H0 and accept H1. Thus, partially employee motivation as an intervening variable has a positive and significant impact in showing the effect of HR Quality on employee performance, that is. Positive influence, meaning that indirectly employee motivation has a real impact in increasing the effect of HR Quality on employee performance.

The quality of human resources plays an important role in improving employee performance. Employees who have good quality at work will usually be more optimal in discussing, giving opinions and ideas for smooth organizational performance. Good quality employees are those that meet the criteria needed in the world of work. These criteria can take the form of soft skills and hard skills. In this case the quality of human resources affects employee performance is supported by employee motivation.

The results of this study are in line with previous studies from Asmaya, (2016) and Marini et al (2014) states that competence has a positive and significant effect on performance. With the quality of human resources, employees will earnestly achieve high performance supported by motivation. Arini, (2015) states that the quality of human resources refers to knowledge, skills, and abilities where this is the basis needed for a company to be able to improve employee performance. Then Nurhayati, (2016) and Firmansyah (2017) in their research concluded that the knowledge possessed by employees such as mastery and good understanding of the vision and mission of the company can improve the quality of each individual to be able to carry out their duties and responsibilities.

The majority of respondents answered very well and well to the statement for employee performance that is having good health at work, having a strong

physical condition, being able to reduce hazardous work, being able to protect themselves from work hazards, having supporting intellectual intelligence, education in the field of work is very support, have mental strength in dealing with problems that occur in the office and competence supports improving work effectiveness.

In the characteristics of the respondents who were most male compared to female respondents, the characteristics of respondents were based on the age of the majority aged between 36-40 years, the characteristics based on education were the highest number of senior high school and the characteristics of respondents with the majority of working tenure of 13-17 years. This shows that the characteristics of the respondents make it clear that there is an influence between the Quality of Human Resources on Employee Performance through SIMPEG Employee Motivation on Employee Performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions in this study are:

1. The results of the research show that the personnel information system (Simpeg) has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning, North Sumatra Province.
2. The results of the study show the personnel information system (Simpeg) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
3. The results of the study indicate that the work environment does not have a positive and significant effect on employee motivation at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.

4. The results of the study indicate that the work environment does not have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
5. The results of the study show that HR quality has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation. The results of the study indicate the value of t count HR quality is higher than the t count of other variables so that the HR Quality variable that is more dominant influences employee motivation when compared to the staffing information system (Simpeg) and Work Environment at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning Office of North Sumatra Province.
6. The results of the study indicate that the quality of human resources has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning, North Sumatra Province.
7. The results of the study show that employee motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
8. The results of the study show that employee motivation as an intervening variable does not have a positive and significant impact in showing the influence of the staffing information system (Simpeg) on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
9. The results of the study show that employee motivation as an intervening variable does not have a positive and significant impact in showing the effect of the work environment on employee

performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.

10. The results of the study show that employee motivation as an intervening variable has a positive and significant impact in showing the effect of HR quality on employee performance at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province.
11. The results showed a Q-Square value of 0.937. This shows the amount of diversity of research data that can be explained by the research model is 93.7%, while the remaining 6.3% is explained by other factors that are outside this research model.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The suggestions in this study are:

1. It is expected that the Ministry can provide procedures for employees in using the staffing information system (Simpeg) so that employees are no longer constrained in inputting and maintaining data into applications. With the Simpeg created by the North Sumatra Provincial Government through the Regional Personnel Agency, it is expected to be able to resolve the constraints related to staffing documents to create paperless personnel administration services (PaketKeras). The Simpeg application can be done by increasing employee motivation in completing all data input and maintaining data that can be done by providing training and socialization so that employees are able to apply SIMPEG and employees are expected to work together to provide information and data regarding the purpose and benefits of SIMPEG applications.
2. It is hoped that the Work Environment will be considered again by UPT SDA Wampu Besitang, the Office of Water Resources, Cipta Karya and Spatial Planning of North Sumatra Province

because the results of the study show that the work environment does not have a positive impact on motivating employees to work and the work environment also does not provide a picture in improving employee performance therefore there are steps that need to be taken so that the work environment provides a real influence. This can be done by providing adequate lighting in the room, making good air circulation in the workspace, providing adequate facilities, and as often as possible to communicate with coworkers.

3. It is expected that the quality of human resources needs to be improved again because it gives a positive influence in encouraging employees to be motivated to work and the existence of good quality human resources can improve employee performance. This can be done by official service and can protect employees from dangerous working conditions. can be done by reducing hazardous work, providing protection from work hazards and increasing competence to be able to increase the effectiveness of employee work.
4. It is expected that employees can be motivated in completing work because of employee motivation can improve employee performance. This can be done by providing salaries, bonuses, attention, rewards, in accordance with the ability of employees, and showing a positive attitude by receiving input or complaints that are experienced by employees so that employees feel safe working at UPT SDA Wampu Besitang and provide career opportunities to be promoted in accordance with employee assessments and abilities.
5. It is expected that employees can improve performance well again, because of the factors that provide a positive picture in improving employee performance well again, this can be done by providing opportunities for employees to work effectively and

giving bonuses to employees if they reach targets established by the organization.

6. The next researcher is expected to be able to add other variables that are suspected to have a major influence on employee performance

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